

Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of some tri-ligand complexes of lanthanides

S. S. Yadav* and R. S. Saxena

Department of Chemistry, Government Raza P.G. College, Rampur-244 901, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 30 June 2008, revised 15 October 2008, accepted 23 October 2008

Abstract : Potentiometric evidences have been cited for the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1; MLL'L' quaternary complexes [$M^{III} = La^{III}, Pr^{III}$ and Nd^{III} , L = ethyleneglycol-bis(β -aminoethylether)- N,N,N',N' -tetraacetic acid (EGTA), L' = pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (PDA) and L'' = 2,2'-dithiodisallylic acid (DTSA)] have been studied potentiometrically with a view to determine their formation constants, thermodynamic parameters and to explore and confirm the possibility of their expanded coordination number. The formation constants $\log K_{MLL'L''}$, $\log K_{MLL'L}$ and $\log K_{MLL'L'}$ for the resulting ternary and quaternary complexes at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.05 KNO_3$) and different temperatures (15 ± 0.1 °C, 25 ± 0.1 °C, 35 ± 0.1 °C and 45 ± 0.1 °C) have been evaluated. The order of formation constants with respect to Ln^{III} ions has been found to be $La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III}$ for both ternary and quaternary complexes whereas ternary < quaternary for mixed-ligand complexes.

Keywords : Stability constant, lanthanides, ternary complexes, quaternary complexes.

Introduction

The formation of ternary complexes of transition metals^{1,2} as well as inner transition metals³ has been studied by different physico-chemical techniques but works on the quaternary complex formation of lanthanides in particular are rare⁴. A survey of literature reveals that lanthanide ions expand their coordination number during formation of complex. This idea led us to investigate some 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, quaternary system of Ln^{III} ions with a view to ascertain the formation and to see the effect on the coordination number of Ln^{III} ion due to addition of one or more ligand.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Standard solutions of standard chemicals (A.R., B.D.H., G.R. or E. Merck) were prepared in conductivity water. Standard solutions of lanthanide nitrates were prepared and standardized by the reported method^{5,6}. The solutions of pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (PDA), potassium hydroxide, potassium nitrate and potassium hydrogenphthalate were prepared by direct weighing and dissolving in double distilled water. EGTA was used in the form of tripotassium salt. The solution of DTSA was prepared in commercially available alcohol.

Instrument and technique :

pH-measurements were carried out with a Toshniwal digital pH meter (CL-46) using a combined glass electrode.

The instrument was standardized against 0.05 M potassium hydrogenphthalate solution (pH 4) before starting each titration. The total volume (50 ml) and ionic strength ($\mu = 0.05 M KNO_3$) also kept constant in the beginning of each titration. Titrations were carried out at different temperatures (15 ± 0.1 , 25 ± 0.1 , 35 ± 0.1 and 45 ± 0.1) °C with the help of an electrically controlled thermostat Scientech Ego/Jumbo German. In above temperature ranges the ambient temperature of Rampur is < 15 °C.

Calculations :

(a) **Formation constants :** The dissociation constant of tripotassium ethyleneglycol-bis(β -aminoethylether)- N,N,N',N' -tetra acetate (K_3 EGTA) ($pK = 9.26 \pm 0.12$), pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (PDA) ($pK_1 = 2.15 \pm 0.05$, $pK_2 = 5.08 \pm 0.08$) were evaluated by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁷. The formation constants ($\log K_{MLL'L''}$, $\log K_{MLL'L}$) of the ternary and ($\log K_{MLL'L''}$) quaternary complexes were calculated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁸.

(b) **Thermodynamic parameters :** Thermodynamic parameters were calculated using standard equations.

$$(i) -\Delta G^\circ = 2.303 RT \log K \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$$

R is gas constant ($1.987 \text{ cal deg}^{-1}$), T = absolute temperature.

$$(ii) \Delta H^\circ = \frac{2.303 RT_1 T_2 (\log \beta_2 - \log \beta_1)}{T_2 - T_1} \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$$

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for the formation constants of quaternary complexes at three different temperatures

Systems	ΔG° (kcal mol ⁻¹)			ΔH° (kcal mol ⁻¹)		
	25 ± 0.1 °C	35 ± 0.1 °C	45 ± 0.1 °C	ΔH_1	ΔH_2	ΔH_3
	La ^{III} -EGTA-PDA-DTSA	-17.25	-16.85	-16.32	-22.38	-22.80
Pr ^{III} -EGTA-PDA-DTSA	-17.86	-17.51	-17.37	-21.59	-21.96	-22.95
Nd ^{III} -EGTA-PDA-DTSA	-18.17	-17.99	-17.63	-20.23	-20.52	-21.12

where β_1 and β_2 are the formation constants at temperatures T_1 and T_2 respectively.

$$(iii) \Delta S^\circ = (\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T$$

Results and discussion

The corresponding curves obtained in all systems of different metal ions at different temperatures were identical and hence for the sake of brevity, the curves for 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, La^{III}-EGTA-PDA-DTSA have only been discussed. A well-defined inflection ($m = 2.6$) before $m = 3$ ($m =$ moles of alkali added per mole ion or the ligand) on the curve 'a' (Fig. 1) indicates the basic salt formation⁹ of metal ions and is in conformity with the observations of Britton¹⁰. Curve 'b' for EGTA and absence of any inflection indicates non-labile nature of carboxylic proton. Curves 'c' and 'd' represent the titration of PDA and DTSA respectively. An inflection at $m = 2$ for both acids exhibits the titration of both the protons of dibasic acids. Curves 'e' and 'f' illustrate the titrations of an equimolar 1 : 1, M^{III}-EGTA and M^{III}-PDA binary species¹¹. An extensive lowering in the initial pH for both the curves may be attributed to the formation of binary complex at pH > 8¹². Curve 'g' for M^{III}-DTSA indicates the appearance of a solid phase at $m > 2$ may be due to the precipitation of metal hydroxide in higher buffer region. Curve 'h' shows the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, M^{III}-EGTA-PDA. The inflections at $m = 3$ and $m = 5$ are due to the formation of mixed-ligand soluble protonated heteroligand species¹³. Curve 'i' depicts the titration of 1 : 1 : 1, M^{III}-EGTA-DTSA species. Two inflections at $m = 3$ and $m = 5$ may be ascribed to the addition of two hydroxyl ions. Curve 'j' illustrates the titration of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1, M^{III}-EGTA-PDA-DTSA quaternary system. An initial lowering in the pH followed by an inflection at $m = 4$ is due to the

Fig. 1. System 1:1:1:1, La^{III}-EGTA-PDA-DTSA : (a) La(NO₃)₃, (b) K₃EGTA, (c) PDA, (d) DTSA, (e) 1:1, La^{III}-EGTA, (f) 1:1, La^{III}-PDA, (g) 1:1, L^{III}-DTSA, (h) 1:1:1, La^{III}-EGTA-PDA, (i) 1:1:1, La^{III}-EGTA-DTSA, (j) 1:1:1:1, La^{III}-EGTA-PDA-DTSA, T = theoretical composite curve, (→) appearance of precipitate, (?) dissolution of precipitate.

simultaneous chelation of all the three ligands. Another inflection at $m = 6$ without any solid phase may be due to the deprotonation of above species and to the addition of one hydroxo group in higher buffer region.

Table 2

Systems	ΔS° (Cal mol ⁻¹)					
	ΔS_1°		ΔS_2°		ΔS_3°	
	15 ± 0.1 °C	25 ± 0.1 °C	25 ± 0.1 °C	35 ± 0.1 °C	35 ± 0.1 °C	45 ± 0.1 °C
La ^{III} -EGTA-PDA-DTSA	17.94	17.73	17.48	17.27	16.94	16.11
Pr ^{III} -EGTA-PDA-DTSA	17.53	16.91	16.63	16.11	15.89	15.40
Nd ^{III} -EGTA-PDA-DTSA	17.45	16.45	15.95	15.13	14.92	14.13

The formation of above mixed-ligand complex is further supported by the following facts : (i) non-appearance of any solid phase in quaternary complex formation region, (ii) non-superimposable nature of theoretical composite curve 'T' with the experimental curve 'j' representing the quaternary system in the region of tri-ligand complex formation and (iii) by the constancy of calculated values of stability constants observed¹⁴ in the region of quaternary complex formation.

Formation constants of mixed-ligand species :

The values of free energy of formation and thermodynamic parameters have given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. The relative order of stabilities for ternary and quaternary species ($\log K_{MLL'}$, $\log K_{MLL''}$ and $\log K_{MLL'L''}$ respectively) in terms of metal ions at different temperatures has been found to be $La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III}$ and may be explained on the basis of decreasing size and increasing ionic potential (charge/radius ratio) of the metal ions. In terms of quaternary and ternary complexes, the observed trend found to be as, quaternary > ternary. It may be due to the increased number of fused chelate rings¹⁵ and extra-stabilization caused by ligand-ligand interactions in quaternary complexes. The value of stability constants decrease with an increase in temperature which refer that the lower temperature favours the formation of complexes. This is further supported by an increase in ionization constants of the ligands with rise in temperature.

Thermodynamic parameters of mixed-ligand species :

The values of free energy of formation (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) changes of resulting quaternary complexes are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. Calculated ΔG° values have been found to be negative in all the cases¹⁶ which indicate that complex formation appears to be almost spontaneous in process^{17,18}. The negative values of ΔH° and positive values of ΔS° indicate that both enthalpy and entropy favour the complex formation. Negative values of enthalpy show the exothermic nature of the reaction and covalent character of the bonds formed between the metal ions and the donor atoms of the ligand. However,

the same values of entropy at different temperatures show that the complex formation reaction remains unaffected by the change of temperature.

Acknowledgement

Authors express their thanks to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Sciences, Khandari, Agra University, Agra and to Prof. Gurmeet Singh of Delhi University, Delhi for giving valuable suggestions.

References

1. R. Kumar, R. C. Sharma and G. K. Chaturvedi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 2503.
2. K. C. Mehta, G. K. Sharma and R. K. Mehta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 656.
3. S. P. Tripathi, G. K. Chaturvedi and R. C. Sharma, *Monatsh. Chemie*, 1978, **109**, 283.
4. S. S. Yadav and R. C. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 9.
5. M. A. Tishchenko, I. I. Zheltvai and N. S. Poloektov, *Z. Neorg. Khim.*, 1974, **19**, 1793.
6. A. M. Hamman and S. A. Ibrahim, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 100.
7. S. Chaberek and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
8. S. Ramamoorthy and M. Santappa, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **9**, 381.
9. T. Moeller and H. E. Kremer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1944, **48**, 395.
10. H. T. S. Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", Chapman and Hall Ltd., 1956, Vol. II, p. 85; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **27**, 127.
11. R. Nagar, I. K. Guad and R. C. Sharma, *J. Electrochem. Soc. (Ind.)*, 1988, **37**, 369.
12. G. K. Carey and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2859.
13. R. Kumar, R. C. Sharma and G. K. Chaturvedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 882.
14. S. S. Yadav and R. C. Sharma, *J. Electrochem. Soc. (India)*, 1994, **43**, 47.
15. D. D. Perrin, "Organic Complexing Agents", John Wiley, 1964, p. 115.
16. S. S. Yadav and R. C. Sharma, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 1994, **10**, 409.
17. K. N. Sharma, V. Pal and M. P. Sawhney, *J. Inst. Chem. (Calcutta)*, 1989, **61**, 149.
18. S. S. Yadav and R. C. Sharma, *Transactions of SAEST*, 2004, **39**, 84.